

KIMYO INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY IN TASHKENT

**«Корееведение
Центральной Азии
в транснациональную эпоху:
взаимопонимание и обмен
знаниями»**

26-27 июня 2026 года

UO'K: 008(575.1+519)(06)

KBK: 71.05(5Узб+5Кор)

ISBN 978-9910-5283-0-9

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20627770>

Loneliness and Ideological Extremity: Survey Evidence from South Korea

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1. Introduction

Contemporary democracies face not only disagreement but the hardening of disagreement into ideological extremity. Extreme positions imply distance from the political center, reduced willingness to compromise, and a stronger tendency to read politics through simplified moral oppositions (Lelkes 2016; Toner et al. 2013; Ryan 2017; van Prooijen and Krouwel 2017, 2019). Existing explanations stress institutions, partisan sorting, elite conflict, media fragmentation, and grievance. Those accounts are indispensable, but they leave a further question: which citizens are more psychologically susceptible to ideological extremes?

This paper examines loneliness as one such source of susceptibility. Loneliness is not the same as living alone, lacking contacts, or being objectively isolated. It is a subjective condition

in which people perceive their social connections as insufficient, unreliable, or emotionally meaningless. Psychological research treats loneliness as perceived social isolation, distinct from actual network size and related but not reducible to depression or anxiety (Cacioppo et al. 2006; Hawkey and Cacioppo 2010; Russell 1996).

The central claim is that loneliness increases susceptibility to ideological extremity, but only under certain political and social conditions. Loneliness matters most when combined with political desire, frustrated efficacy, and social interaction. The key figure is therefore not the isolated loner but the socially connected yet subjectively disconnected citizen: someone with enough interaction to encounter ideological frames and enough loneliness to find extreme frames emotionally compelling.

Empirically, the paper uses the 2024 Korean Social Integration Survey, a national survey of South Korean adults. South Korea is a useful case because political conflict has intensified, while mass ideology remains multidimensional and historically layered (Cheong and Haggard 2023; Han 2022). This allows the analysis to separate ideological direction from ideological extremity.

The findings support this expectation. Ideologically extreme respondents report higher loneliness than non-extreme respondents, and multivariate logit estimates show that loneliness significantly predicts ideological extremity. The association is strongest among respondents with high political interest and low political efficacy, among respondents above a network-size threshold, and among younger cohorts. Yet loneliness is associated with more liberal, not conservative, issue positions in this case, suggesting that loneliness produces susceptibility to ideological intensity rather than a fixed ideological direction.

The article makes three contributions. It adds loneliness to research on the psychological foundations of extremity, clarifies that loneliness need not produce right-wing or authoritarian politics, and identifies political interest, low efficacy, network interaction, and cohort location as conditions under which loneliness becomes politically consequential.

2. Loneliness, Ideological Extremity, and Political Desire

2.1. Ideological extremity as distance, not direction

Ideological direction refers to whether citizens are liberal or conservative, redistributionist or market-oriented, traditionalist or individualist, hawkish or dovish. Extremity refers to distance from the center. This distinction matters because psychological features such as dogmatism, overconfidence, threat sensitivity, and intolerance can appear at both ideological poles (Brandt et al. 2014; van Prooijen and Krouwel 2017, 2019). This study therefore conceptualizes ideological extremity as distance from the sample mean across issue-position scales rather than support for a particular ideological camp. This approach is especially appropriate in South Korea, where economic views, value orientations, and attitudes toward

North Korea do not always map neatly onto a single Western left–right continuum.

2.2. Loneliness as subjective disconnection

Loneliness is a perceived deficit in meaningful connection. A person may have few contacts without feeling lonely, while another may interact frequently yet feel unseen or cut off. Because loneliness involves perceived social isolation, it can produce negative affect, vigilance, pessimism, and diminished trust (Cacioppo et al. 2006; Hawkey and Cacioppo 2010). Recent work links loneliness to populist radical–right support and right–extreme radicalization (Peterson et al. 2025; Langenkamp 2025). This article treats those findings as evidence that loneliness can become politically consequential, not as proof that loneliness is intrinsically right–wing. Loneliness creates a demand for connection, recognition, certainty, and significance; ideological supply determines how that demand is expressed. Accordingly, loneliness may attach to conservative backlash, left–liberal moral politics, populist resentment, nationalist grievance, or political withdrawal depending on the surrounding context. The theoretical task is therefore to identify the conditions under which subjective disconnection becomes ideological extremity.

2.3. Mechanisms: certainty, significance, fusion, and social translation

First, loneliness can generate a search for certainty. Uncertainty–identity theory suggests that people facing self–uncertainty are drawn to groups with clear boundaries and directive norms (Hogg 2014). Second, loneliness can intensify the quest for significance by making ordinary recognition feel unavailable; extreme ideology can transform private pain into public meaning (Kruglanski et al. 2014). Third, loneliness may make identity fusion attractive because the group promises belonging and purpose (Swann et al. 2009; Varmann et al. 2024). Fourth, loneliness requires social translation. Private disconnection becomes politically meaningful when interaction supplies narratives that convert loneliness into grievance, resentment, solidarity, or conviction. Online misogynistic communities illustrate how loneliness can be transformed into antagonistic politics through shared discourse (Tietjen and Tirkkonen 2023). The implication is that loneliness works through, not outside, social interaction.

2.4. Research hypotheses

The baseline expectation is that loneliness is associated with ideological extremity. This does not imply that every lonely individual becomes extreme, nor that loneliness is a sufficient cause of extremity. It implies that subjective disconnection increases the probability of holding ideological positions that are distant from the sample mean.

H1. Individuals experiencing higher loneliness are more likely to exhibit ideological extremity.

The first conditional expectation concerns political desire. Loneliness should matter most among respondents who are politically interested but low in efficacy: politics matters to them,

but ordinary channels feel ineffective.

H1a. The association between loneliness and ideological extremity is stronger among individuals with high political interest and low political efficacy.

The social translation mechanism implies that objective interaction should not simply reduce the political relevance of loneliness. If interaction supplies ideological frames, loneliness may matter more above a minimum level of social contact.

H1b. The association between loneliness and ideological extremity is stronger when social interaction exceeds a minimum threshold.

Generational differences are also likely. Younger cohorts have been socialized in more digitally mediated, precarious, and affectively polarized environments, so loneliness may have stronger ideological consequences among younger citizens.

H1c. The association between loneliness and ideological extremity varies across age cohorts.

3. Research Design

3.1. Data

The analysis uses the 2024 Korean Social Integration Survey. The survey was conducted in August and September 2024 and includes 8,251 adults aged 19 and above. It uses multistage stratified random sampling and primarily in-person interviews. Because the design is observational and cross-sectional, the estimates should be interpreted as associations rather than causal effects.

3.2. Measurement

Loneliness. The main explanatory variable is a three-item index based on feeling lonely, thinking of suicide, and feeling that nobody knows the respondent well. Each item is measured on a four-point scale. The items are combined using an unrotated factor score and rescaled from 0 to 1. Because the index includes a severe distress item, robustness analyses also use the individual items separately.

Ideology. Ideology is measured using economic, value, and North Korea-related issue positions. The items are combined into an unrotated factor score and rescaled from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating more liberal or progressive positions in the Korean context.

Extreme ideology. The dependent variable is a binary indicator based on distance from the sample mean in the ideology factor score. Respondents beyond two standard deviations from the mean are classified as ideologically extreme. This yields 480 extreme respondents, or 5.8 percent of the sample, and captures distance from the center rather than conservative or liberal direction.

Political desire, efficacy, and social interaction. Political interest and political efficacy test whether loneliness matters most among respondents who care about politics but feel ineffective. Network size, measured as the average number of daily contacts, tests whether social interaction conditions the political translation of loneliness.

3.3. Estimation strategy

The baseline analysis estimates logit models in which ideological extremity is regressed on loneliness and demographic and socioeconomic controls:

$$Pr(Extreme_i = 1) = \text{logit}^{-1}(\alpha + \beta Loneliness_i + X_i B),$$

where $Extreme_i$ indicates ideological extremity, $Loneliness_i$ is the rescaled loneliness index, and X_i includes age cohort, gender, income or class, marital status, employment status, student status, and unemployment status. Because logit coefficients are difficult to interpret substantively, the results emphasize predicted probabilities and marginal effects.

Table 1. Logit Models Predicting Ideological Extremity

	Bivariate	Multivariate w/o covariates	Multivariate w/ covariates
Loneliness	1.279*** (0.233)	1.302*** (0.233)	1.272*** (0.235)
Political interest		0.269*** (0.070)	0.258*** (0.072)
Political efficacy		-0.119** (0.052)	-0.121** (0.052)
Network size		0.085*** (0.017)	0.087*** (0.017)
Age group (30s)		0.025 (0.173)	-0.356* (0.194)
Age group (40s)		-0.154 (0.175)	-0.698*** (0.209)
Age group (50s)		-0.211 (0.171)	-0.870*** (0.214)
Age group (60s+)		-0.022 (0.152)	-0.732*** (0.219)
Obs.	8251	8251	8251
Log likelihood	-1816.897	-1792.195	-1775.362
Pseudo R-squared	0.0077	0.0212	0.0304

Note: Standard errors in parenthesis; * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$; 20s is the reference group for the age variable.

4. Results

The descriptive evidence is consistent with H1. Extreme respondents report higher loneliness than non-extreme respondents (difference = 0.047, SE = 0.009). Because the index ranges from 0 to 1 and has a standard deviation of 0.18, the gap is substantively meaningful. The multivariate logit estimates confirm this pattern. Table 1 shows that loneliness is positive and statistically significant across bivariate, multivariate, and covariate-adjusted specifications. Individual-item robustness models yield the same general conclusion.

Substantively, loneliness is associated with distance from moderate ideological positions. This is consistent with theories linking distress, uncertainty, and significance seeking to extremity, though the evidence remains associational rather than causal (Hogg 2014; Kruglanski et al. 2014; van Prooijen and Krouwel 2019).

Political desire conditions. The conditional analysis supports H1a. The loneliness-extremity association is significant among respondents with high political interest and low political efficacy (Figure 2). This profile combines attention, frustration, and subjective disconnection: politics matters, but ordinary channels appear ineffective. This result distinguishes loneliness from apathy. A lonely but politically uninterested person may withdraw from politics, while an efficacious person may channel dissatisfaction through ordinary participation. The highest-

Figure 2. Predicted probability of extreme ideology by loneliness and political desire

risk profile is politically attentive alienation. This pattern links survey evidence to theories of uncertainty and significance. Political efficacy may be the bridge: citizens who feel ineffective may be drawn to ideological positions that provide moral clarity and a stronger sense of agency. **Social interaction conditions.** The results for network size support H1b. The loneliness–extremity association becomes significant when social interaction exceeds a threshold, estimated around 0.3 in Figure 3 (left). This challenges the image of extremity as simple isolation. The politically consequential form may be loneliness within interaction.

This finding fits the social translation account. Loneliness supplies the affective condition, while conversations, online groups, political communities, and media–sharing environments supply frames that interpret loneliness as injustice, betrayal, exclusion, or moral insight. The survey cannot observe discourse directly, but the network result is consistent with this mechanism.

Generational heterogeneity. Figure 3 (right) shows that the marginal effect of loneliness on extreme ideology is strongest among younger cohorts, supporting H1c. The association is largest for respondents in their twenties and thirties and weaker among older cohorts.

Several mechanisms may explain this age pattern. Younger citizens may experience loneliness in politically saturated digital spaces, face stronger status anxiety and labor–market insecurity, be less anchored in traditional organizations, and encounter different ideological supply than older citizens.

Figure 3. Network size cohort specific effect of loneliness on extreme ideology

5. Discussion

The findings show that loneliness is politically consequential but also conditional. Network size points to the need to distinguish interaction volume, network diversity, and ideological homogeneity (Eveland and Hively 2009). A large homogeneous network may intensify extremity by reinforcing confidence and group boundaries (Wojcieszak 2010; Stroud 2010), whereas cross-cutting networks may moderate extremity by exposing citizens to disagreement and alternative rationales (Mutz 2002; Huckfeldt et al. 2004; Mutz and Mondak 2006).

The cohort pattern also requires further research. The current evidence cannot adjudicate among digital mediation, precarity, organizational decline, and cohort-specific ideological supply. It nevertheless suggests that loneliness is not merely an individual trait; it is historically and generationally structured.

An additional OLS analysis shows that loneliness is positively associated with the ideology score, meaning lonelier respondents are more liberal on the issue-position factor. Although this does not align with previous studies linking loneliness to radical-right support elsewhere (Langenkamp 2025; Peterson et al. 2025), it further implies that the direction of loneliness is context-dependent. Loneliness may generate demand for meaning and recognition, but political context determines whether that demand attaches to conservative backlash, liberal redistribution, anti-establishment progressivism, nationalist grievance, or other ideological packages.

6. Conclusion

This paper asked who is more susceptible to ideological extremity. Using nationally representative survey evidence from South Korea, it shows that lonely respondents are more likely to be ideologically extreme. The association is robust across alternative loneliness measures and is strongest among politically interested but inefficacious respondents, socially interacting respondents above a network threshold, and younger cohorts.

The broader implication is that loneliness is not inherently reactionary. It can attach to different ideological projects depending on context, cohort, and political supply. Democratic politics therefore cannot be understood only through institutions, parties, and issue preferences. It also depends on whether citizens feel socially connected, politically efficacious, and recognized by ordinary channels of political life.

The study has limitations. The data are cross-sectional, so the analysis cannot establish whether loneliness precedes extremity or whether extremity increases loneliness. The loneliness index includes suicidal ideation, which captures severe distress and should not be treated as a standard loneliness item without caution. The extremity measure is relative to the sample distribution and should be tested with alternative thresholds, absolute distances, and pooled years. Finally, the network measure captures size but not ideological composition.

Future work should use validated loneliness scales, panel data, survey experiments, qualitative interviews, and online community analysis to identify causal mechanisms. It should also measure network diversity and exposure to cross-cutting disagreement. The present study establishes the core association and shows why loneliness deserves a central place in research on ideological hardening.

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